

THE ROLE OF LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN NON- PHILOLOGICAL DIRECTION STUDENTS

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Abstract: The article deals with the problems of listening and its types. Taking into consideration, when teaching foreign non-philology students, given their professional orientation different types of listening should be improved.

Keywords: listening, communication, learning, auditing, auditing competence, professional-oriented, audio message.

A number of reforms are being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to comprehensively educate young people in the spirit of full-fledged, erudite people capable of independent thinking and initiative. In particular, the teaching of foreign languages with interdisciplinary integration is of great importance. "In our country, there is a need to train modern personnel who know several languages, conduct scientific work in foreign languages, and improve the methodology of language teaching⁵⁶." And also, the organization of methodological work; improving teaching methods based on an integrative approach; study of foreign experience; the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of professionally oriented English at the technological faculties of non-philological universities is one of the priority tasks.

One of the main sources of gaining knowledge in teaching foreign non-philologists is listening, since mastering a foreign language is impossible without the ability to listen and understand sounding speech. Introduced by Don Brown in 1930 in Teaching Aural English "The term" listening" is given the following most complete definition: "Listening is a complex mental process of perception, recognition and understanding of speech, accompanied by active processing of the information received in connection with the auditor's linguistic and pragmatic experience and evaluation of perceived information in inner speech" .

There are communicative and educational listening. If educational listening acts as a learning tool, serves as a way to introduce language material, then communicative

⁵⁶ Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on March 5, 2018 during a visit to the Isokhon boarding school Ibrat Turakurgan district of Namangan region . - Ibrat - Mazhm . (data from the appeal on 10/16/2018)

listening is the goal of learning and is a complex speech ability to understand speech by ear during its one-time reproduction.

When teaching foreign students -non-philologists in a foreign language, the most significant is teaching educational listening.

Being a receptive type of speech activity, listening is the process of perceiving and understanding speech by ear, where perception is the analysis and synthesis of the material means of the language, and understanding is the result of the analysis and synthesis of the semantic meanings of these means, that is, this listening is simultaneous with the understanding of sounding speech, which allows you to do a certain conclusion, which is preceded by the analysis and synthesis of the meaning of multi -level units (phonemes, morphemes, words, sentences).

All information in the study of a foreign language is addressed to visual and auditory analyzers. By stimulating the speech activity of students, listening provides management of the learning process and is used to introduce foreign students to new language and speech material.

Given the different functions of listening in the learning process, different levels of listening comprehension, the following types of listening are distinguished :

1. With full understanding (the speech of the teacher and the student, if it does not contain unfamiliar phenomena);
2. With an understanding of the main content (for example, listening to determine what it says, authentic functional texts);
3. With selective understanding (for example, listen to an ad to understand if it applies to you, etc.);
4. Listening with a critical assessment.

Therefore, the purpose of training in listening as a type of speech activity is the development of these types of it. However, when teaching listening , one should take into account both the goals and the nature of understanding the information, and the state of attention of a foreign student at the time of listening. According to the purpose, there are exploratory , introductory , activity (detailed), critical (interactive) listening.

Getting the right information in a variety of communication situations is the goal of an inquirer listening . The subsequent transfer of information is not expected, this is

information for yourself. By the nature of perception, this type of listening can be both global and global - detailed, with the latter predominating.

Introductory listening does not imply a special setting for memorization and mandatory subsequent use of information extracted from popular science, professional, socio-political literature. Introductory Listening can be divided into three types:

- 1) cognitive;
- 2) entertaining;
- 3) informative - entertaining.

By its nature, it is predominantly global – detailed.

Detailed listening is aimed at capturing and remembering information in detail for subsequent mandatory immediate reproduction. The nature of perception in such listening is globally - detailed. With a delayed reproduction of the main provisions of the perceived, the nature of perception is global. This type of listening requires special training.

According to the nature of understanding information, fragmentary, global (synthetic), detailed (analytical) are distinguished. When teaching foreign students in-non-philologists should develop global (perception of the text as a whole), detailed (understanding, if not all, then the most important blocks of the text, depends on the attitude given by the speaker) and critical (based on global and detailed perception and requires critical listening) perception speech. Critical perception, being very specific, requires the development of the following skills:

- 1) distinguish facts from opinions;
- 2) determine the point of view of the speaker, his emotional state;
- 3) recognize the main stylistic devices (for example, irony, hyperbole) and understand what the speaker wanted to convey using them;
- 4) understand the subtext;
- 5) express their point of view about what they heard, based on their own life experience;
- 6) to question what they heard and correlate it with their own life position.

Listening with a critical assessment is of great value for the personal development of foreign students and the development of their value orientations.

The auditing process cannot be fully automated. For a successful listening process, such initial abilities as memory, attention, hearing, imitation, guessing, forecasting are necessary.

The process of listening begins with perception, which depends on the selection of semantic landmarks: intonation (as a sign of the connection of words in a sentence), rhythm, pauses, logical stresses, speech tempo. And learning to listen should start with the use of sentences in which there are no more than 5-7 words, gradually increasing their length, you can bring their volume to 15-18 words.

Probabilistic prediction of the statement comes to the fore when listening. When deciphering the speech flow, the sounding speech is divided into separate grammatical and semantic links: phrases, phrases, words.

When teaching listening, it is necessary to develop the following skills:

- 1) highlight the main thing, not paying attention to details that are not essential for understanding the main content, discarding the secondary;
- 2) to achieve understanding of this basic information, showing speech activity and initiative;
- 3) ignore language difficulties and obstacles.

So, the ultimate goal in teaching foreign students-non-philologists listening is well-formed auditory skills.

When teaching foreign students-non-philologists, taking into account their professional orientation, attention should be paid to the development of various types of listening, and in the structure of skills, teach them to transfer skills from one type of listening to another in accordance with the objectives and goals of training. The effectiveness of learning to listen largely depends on this.

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